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The Magnitude of Conversion to Judaism in Israel

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Policy Paper No. 08.2026

Jerusalem, May 2026

Taub Center for Social Policy Studies in Israel

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Please cite this publication as:

Weinreb, A. (2026). *The Magnitude of Conversion to Judaism in Israel*. Taub Center for Social Policy Studies in Israel. <https://doi.10.5281/zenodo.19564781>

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The Magnitude of Conversion to Judaism in Israel

Alex Weinreb

Introduction

Conversion to Judaism may sound like a trivial issue for Israeli demography, or the demography of Jews in general. After all, although Judaism permits conversion — unlike, for example, the Druze religion or Zoroastrianism — and was even a missionizing religion into the second century CE, it has not actively sought converts or encouraged conversion since around the 3rd century (Cohen, 1999; Hayes, 1999). This approach to conversion, anchored in tannaitic codification of *halakha*, had its intended demographic effect: for more than 1,500 years, converts to Judaism were rare, making conversion to Judaism demographically trivial.¹ Conversion out of Judaism — what Carlebach (2001) refers to as “escaping the ranks of the scorned and detested” — was, of course, a very different story.

Three cultural shifts across Western liberal societies, in which the vast majority of today's Jews reside, suggest that conversion to Judaism is now a much more realistic option, much less costly in social terms, and therefore much less demographically trivial than it has been at any point in time over those 1,500 years.

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1 As explained by Rabbi David Bas, a judge in the Special Conversion Bet Din since 2001, “In Christian and Muslim countries, conversion to Judaism was prohibited by law, and converts risked death. Therefore, it was done only in secret. It is difficult to know how many converted, but it is assumed that not many did. In Western Europe, conversion became legitimate after the French Revolution, and in Central Europe and further east — only after World War I.” (Personal communication, 2024)

First, Jews are now a high-status population. In almost every politically and culturally liberal country in which they reside, Jews have higher than average levels of education and income, a disproportionate presence among cultural, intellectual and scientific elites, and they are much more visible than in past periods (Cooperman et al., 2021; Dershowitz, 1997; Endelman, 2002). This should increase the appeal of Judaism, since in contemporary liberal societies there is greater “cultural consumption” of high-prestige goods, including religious goods (DiMaggio, 1987; Sherkat & Wilson, 1994). *Second*, earlier patterns of assimilation have led to significant growth in what can be called “Jewish-adjacent” populations — including the children or grandchildren of Jews — who can legitimately point to associations that they would like to explore and possibly exploit. We revisit this below. *Third*, a change in attitudes to “identity,” including religious identity, facilitates that exploration. In modern liberal societies, identity is no longer merely ascribed; it is also selected. This is true across multiple domains, not only religion (Giddens, 1991; Taylor, 2003).

The Pew 2021 survey of the American Jewish population provides some evidence that conversion is making an impact on the Jewish population in the US, which for now continues to be home to the world’s largest Jewish population. The survey found that among adults, around 8% of Conservative Jews, 7% of Reform Jews, 2% of Jews with no denominational affiliation and 1% of Orthodox Jews grew up without a single Jewish parent and were not raised Jewish in any way (Ausubel et al., 2021). Similar results were found in Pew’s 2013 survey (Pinker, 2021). Adding children to these figures, and thinking about marriage and family in the second and third generations after a conversion, it is easy to see how much conversion is affecting the composition of America’s Jewish population, at least outside Orthodox Judaism. In demographic terms, this means that substantial out-migration from Judaism in the form of assimilation, a longstanding concern within Jewish communities, is being at least partly offset by in-migration into Judaism.

In Israel, additional factors come into play. Notably, as a direct result of the Law of Return, which grants the children or grandchildren of Jews, and their spouses and children, rights of residence and citizenship in Israel, even if they are not halachically Jewish, there has been massive growth in the pool of

potential converts in Israel.² In formal Israeli statistics, these halakhic non-Jews are categorized as “Others” in Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS) ethnic tables, and as “without a religious classification” in CBS religion tables — there is almost complete overlap between these two categories.

In this research paper, I refer to this population — which exceeded 470,000 Israelis in 2025 and was the fastest growing subpopulation in the country in the five years preceding October 7, 2023, even outpacing the Haredi population (Weinreb, 2023) — as the main source of potential converts. It is important to emphasize that I am not suggesting that members of the Other population want to convert or should convert. My point is simply statistical: the vast majority of converts in Israel stem from this population. That is to be expected. Members of the Other population live in Jewish-majority towns in the world’s only Jewish-majority country, in which language, calendar, life-course and education are infused with Jewish-Israeli content, even in the most “secular” sanctuaries. A natural outcome of living in this Jewish-Israeli milieu is what Cohen and Susser (2009) refer to as “sociological conversion,” that is, assimilation into Jewish-dominated models of Israeli identity.³ But the more

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- 2 Another potential source of growth in the Other population appears to be the partners of Israelis met while the latter were traveling, working or studying overseas, or the former visiting Israel. Israel’s high-growth and low-unemployment levels meant that many more of these couples chose to live in Israel than was the case in the more impoverished decades of the late 20th century. Unfortunately, the CBS does not publish data on this phenomenon. Nor is there a scholarly literature on it unlike, for example, the much less common mixed Jewish-Arab (Christian and Muslim) marriages (Karkabi-Sabbah, 2017; Meler & Oryan 2024).
 - 3 Ben-Gurion recognized the naturalness of this process as early as 1958. In a political crisis precipitated by a (secular) Minister of Interior’s decision to register the children of two non-Jewish immigrants as Jewish, the National Religious Party resigned from the ruling coalition. In response, Ben-Gurion wrote (quoted in Cohen & Susser, 2009): “The Jewish collective in Israel is not the same as the Jewish collective in the Diaspora. Here, we are not a minority under the pressure of an alien culture. There is no fear here of Jews assimilating into non-Jewish surroundings as happens in some free prosperous states: Quite the opposite. There is the tendency and possibility of mild assimilation of non-Jews into the Jewish people — especially mixed married families that immigrate to Israel.”

It is worth noting that despite Ben-Gurion’s apparent view that sociological conversion is sufficient, the 1958 crisis was resolved by granting the National Religious Party authority over the Ministry of Interior, which allowed it to use criteria anchored in orthodox Jewish law. That meant placing religious identity, based on either matrilineal descent or an orthodox conversion, at the center. A subsequent crisis in 1970 (following a Supreme Court ruling in the Shalit case regarding the religious status of a Jewish Israeli’s children) led to a more formal codification of status and rights. Religious identity of Jews would follow the standard halachic lines of matrilineal descent, but the Right of Return was extended to all non-Jewish family members.

important question, from the perspective of this paper, is how much living in this Jewish-Israeli milieu leads to religious conversion, since that signals fuller assimilation into the dualistic national and religious Israeli Jewish identity.

Two simple empirical questions arise from this discussion. How common is religious conversion (to Judaism) in Israel? And how demographically significant is it? Answering these questions is the primary goal of this paper.

This is an important exercise for three reasons. First, a variety of observers have asserted that levels of conversion are low and insignificant (Cohen & Susser, 2009; Fisher, 2015).⁴ Others are less convinced (Bas, 2007). Till now, no robust estimate rooted in a methodologically appropriate method has been available to help resolve, or at least advance, this debate.

Second, better estimates can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of conversion as public policy. This is important because conversion in Israel, unlike in all other high-income countries, is state-sponsored: the State of Israel pays for conversion classes, for the salaries of the *dayanim* (religious judges) on conversion committees, and for the administrative process in general.⁵ As noted by Fisher (2015), questions about financing have been a focus of ongoing debates regarding the optimal framework for conversion

4 Cohen and Susser's (2009, p. 63) conclusion is representative: "Even though there have been attempts to make the conversion process more 'user-friendly' and straightforward, the number of ex-Soviet immigrants who are interested in conversion is very small. They are, in their vast majority, secular non-believers and conversion is overwhelmingly about religious belief and practice. . . . As matters stand at the present, conversion cannot be counted upon to clarify the identity of the non-Jewish Jews."

Fisher (2015, p. 46) makes a similar point: "The state conversion apparatus was established to address the issue of assimilation and its consequences for the State of Israel as a Jewish State. After nearly twenty years of activity, one can sum up and say that the apparatus of conversion has not accomplished the national mission entrusted to it — the number of converts from among *olim* who arrived from the former USSR is too low" (own translation).

5 Since Israel's establishment, building on a law first encoded in 1927 during the British Mandate, religious conversion has been under the authority of each religious tradition's respective leadership, where those authorities are publicly funded. For Jews, this leadership is Israel's Chief Rabbinate. Actual organization of conversion has shifted across the last 30 years. Until 1995, conversions were under the authority of regional rabbinical courts. The massive *aliya* from the ex-Soviet Union and large *aliya* from Ethiopia gave rise to a more centralized approach under a Conversion Administration that operated from 1995–2000, its incorporation into the Ministry of Religion as a State Conversion System from 2000–2003, and then, its subsequent importation into the Prime Minister's Office in 2003 as the Authority for Religious Services.

and conversion criteria, with the latter becoming more stringent over the last decade (Itim, 2024). Moreover, those debates are occurring amid growth in the primary conversion pool. DellaPergola (2022) estimates that approximately 18 million people outside Israel have rights to immigrate to Israel under the Law of Return, of whom around 10 million are not halachically Jewish. If even a small portion of that 10 million exercises its rights, and Israel wants to encourage religious conversion as a way to preserve a Jewish majority or foster a shared “civil religion” — as the ever-pragmatic Machiavelli called it in his *Discourses on Livy* — then it will need to significantly scale-up the conversion infrastructure while making it more effective and efficient. In that case, a robust estimate of current rates can provide a baseline against which future conversion levels can be compared.

The third reason is more relevant to applied demography as a discipline. As is well known, Israel’s approach to matters of religion and state is different to that of other liberal countries. Like its neighboring Arab countries, Israel inherited the Ottoman “Millet System” that gave religious autonomy to non-Muslim “confessional communities”, basing this autonomy in the recognition that people place great store in their religious identity — irrespective of their religiosity. This approach is reflected at the individual level in the differences between religions in the ways they manage marriage, divorce, burial, and so on. At the government level, it is reflected in the ability of the CBS and other government bodies to collect data on the religion of every individual in the population. Both of these practices are in direct contrast to the approach in many liberal countries, which not only ignore the religious identity of the citizen but even prohibit government agencies — including national statistical offices — from collecting data on citizens’ religion.⁶ In fact, the importance of religious identity in Israeli demography makes conversion rates a central demographic component, at least potentially, in any analysis of demographic change. For while the classic components of population change in general demography are births, deaths, and migration, in Israel, conversion effectively becomes a fourth component: Changes in the size of sub-populations can also be caused by conversion, even though the CBS, like its counterparts in other developed countries, does not record it.

6 Examples include Italy, Germany, Japan, France, and the US.

The paper proceeds in two main sections. I begin by showing why the conventional interpretation of crude conversion rates is flawed. I then look at conversion by age and sex and employ a Life Table approach — a classic demographic method — to generate age- and sex-specific estimates of the probability of conversion. I end by adding a simple simulation that considers the longer-term impacts through female converts' subsequent fertility, since that is the key to evaluating the full demographic impact of conversion. Up to this point, all estimates are conducted on 2022 data. I then replicate them on data from 2020 and 2021.

It is important to clarify that my focus in this paper is not on whether Israel should encourage conversion and, if so, how stringent the criteria should be, how much the state needs to be involved, how decentralized or even privatized the system can be, and whether Israel should be more restrictive regarding rights of return. Some of these questions are addressed by Bas (2007) and others by Fisher (2015). Instead, and as mentioned above, my focus is narrowly empirical. It is to generate more methodologically valid estimates of the magnitude of conversion from the perspective of demography as an academic discipline.

My argument, likewise, is quite simple. Even though crude conversion rates of older non-Jewish immigrants in Israel are low, conversion in general is much more demographically significant because it occurs at much higher rates among the young. Specifically, current age-specific conversion rates imply that about 40% of women and 25% of men who arrive in Israel as children and are classified as belonging to the Other population, convert to Judaism by age 30. Those much higher lifetime conversion rates are consistent with the idea that conversion in Israel merits more serious demographic treatment than it has historically received. It should no longer be treated as a trivial demographic issue. Nor can the existing conversion system be dismissed as an abject failure.

A first (misleading) glance

At first glance, the demographic impact of conversion looks absolutely trivial. As shown in Table 1, across the 2020–2023 period, there were 11,420 conversions in Israel. Even if, in the absence of COVID-related restrictions in 2020 and the Gaza War that began in October, 2023, the number of converts in 2020 and 2023 would have been closer to the 2021 and 2022 totals, these are still very small numbers relative to Israel's Other or Jewish population. They

imply that only around 0.7% of Israel's Other population in 2022 converted, and that these new converts added less than 0.05% to Israel's Jewish population of 7.17 million in mid-2023. The data that Fisher (2015, p. 47) presents on conversions from 1996–2014 are similar.

Table 1. Total number of converts to Judaism, by sex

	Women	Men	Total
2020	1,614	834	2,448
2021	2,095	1,254	3,349
2022	2,181	1,208	3,389
2023	1,551	683	2,234
All years	7,441	3,979	11,420

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: released by the Population and Immigration Authority in response to Freedom of Information request 409598

Using data in this way is not an appropriate measure of demographic impact. There are three reasons.

First, the data in Table 1 tell us nothing about variation in conversion rates by age and sex. These are the two most important variables in standard demographic analyses since all demographic parameters have a distinct age pattern, and they also typically vary by sex (and vary across time by age and sex). The same is true of conversion in Israel, as we show below. Inferring too much from Table 1 is therefore akin to using “crude rates” in demography (e.g., Crude Death Rate, Crude Birth Rate) instead of measures derived from “age-specific rates” (like the total fertility rate or life expectancy). Crude rates are as likely to mislead as they are to inform.

Second, the data presented in Table 1 ignore the cumulative effect of conversion on a given age cohort across a lifetime. For example, the fact that 2,181 women converted in 2022 tells us nothing about how many years they were in Israel prior to conversion, how many Other women there were of the same age and duration in Israel who had converted prior to 2022, or how many converted in 2022 itself. This is especially important in the Israeli case given the rapid growth in Israel's Other population.

Third, the data in Table 1 ignore second-order effects of conversion, especially for women. Under the traditional (orthodox) interpretive traditions that determine Jewish religious identity in Israel, a child's Jewish identity is carried through the matriline: the child is Jewish if its biological mother (at the time of birth, not conception, according to conventional halachic rulings) is Jewish; otherwise, the child is not Jewish. This matrilineal norm effectively connects age and gender. When a woman converts before childbirth, every child she subsequently bears adds to the demographic impact of her conversion. In the Israeli context, the child is added to the stock of Jewish children, not Other children. This point has been raised by other researchers (Bas, 2007).⁷

Conversion by age and sex

Figure 1 shows the distinct age and sex profile of three populations in Israel in 2022. The panel on the left is Israel's Jewish population in mid-2022. Males are arrayed on the left, females on the right, and each row represents the number of people of a given age. When people convert, they join this population.

The right-hand panel shows the number of people who converted at every age. It uses data received from the Population Registry in response to a Freedom of Information request focused on conversion to Judaism.⁸ The figure confirms how distinct conversion patterns are by age. Modal ages of conversion are

7 A fourth problem with the Table 1 data is that they may underestimate conversion rates. This problem is less important empirically compared to the other reasons detailed here, so I will suffice with a brief explanation. The Table 1 data ignore a core principle of demographic accounting, which is to estimate the probability of a given event occurring over time in relation to the population that is "at risk" from a particular starting point. Given that the conversion process typically takes a few years to complete, the probability of conversion needs to be linked to the population at risk — that is, a population of potential converts — at the start of the process. Likewise, rates of conversion need to be linked to person-years at risk, which also implies careful delineation of a starting point. Inferring rates by comparing the numbers shown in Table 1 (converts in the last year) to the number of Others in the same year errs in this regard. The latter includes recent arrivals, none of whom can realistically be thought to be "at risk" of conversion since they have not been in Israel long enough. This leads to an underestimate of the rate of conversion.

8 The changes in the population registry do not reflect State-sponsored Orthodox conversions fully since, according to the ruling of the Supreme Court, other Orthodox conversions can trigger a change in the registry. However, the number of conversions carried out outside the State system is very small (Rabbi David Bas, personal communication, 2024).

between 18 and 23. Among women, around one-third of conversions occurred at those ages in 2021 and 2022, with that figure climbing to 45% during 2023 — this is consistent with conversion programs offered during mandatory military service or shortly thereafter.

Figure 1. Jews, Others, and people completing conversion, by age and sex, 2022

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Israel's Other population, from which almost all converts in Israel are drawn, is shown in the middle panel. It has a completely different age structure to both Jews and converts. The largest age group in the Other population stretch from people's early 30s to early 50s, especially for women. Even though each of these panels has a very different scale, one can easily infer that conversion rates are higher where the Other population is relatively small: in early childhood and army ages up to people's mid-20s. At other ages, especially above 40, the conversion rates are low.

The right-hand panel also points to the substantial differences in the ratio of female to male converts across age. We show this in more detail in Figure 2. Up to people's mid-teens, there is a roughly 1:1 ratio of female to male converts. This makes sense since conversion at these ages is more a choice of parents, and there is no inherent reason for them to prefer converting boys over girls

or vice-versa. However, from the age that people make their own choice about whether to convert, the ratio leans more heavily female. The female:male ratio reaches around 4:1 during army ages, and then fluctuates in the 2:1–3:1 range until around age 60. There appear to be several reasons for this gender difference: the obligation for male converts to undergo circumcision may deter some potential candidates; social pressures related to conversion in Israel, which are almost certainly connected to the matrilineal inheritance of religious identity, are exerted more on women than on men; and daily religious practice places more demands on men than on women in terms of specific commandments (women are exempt from the *minyan* in the synagogue, do not put on *tefillin*, as less obligated to learn, etc.). In any case, the preponderance of female converts over male converts aligns with conversion patterns reported throughout history from the time of the Second Temple (Zilm, 2008) until today. For example, in a comprehensive study conducted in the United States in the 1980s, it was found that 77% of converts were women (Lerer & Mayer, 1989).

Figure 2. Ratio of female to male converts to Judaism, 2020–2023

Note: The dotted line indicates the three-year average of the female-to-male convert ratio.

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Life Table approach

The distinct age- and sex-specific conversion patterns shown in Figure 1 underscore the importance of moving away from crude measures of conversion when assessing the overall magnitude of conversion and its demographic impact. We do this using a Life Table methodology. This is the same methodology that demographers use to calculate the probability of death at any given age, and from which they generate estimates of life expectancy. Using it here allows us to generate age-specific conversion rates while avoiding the first two problems with the raw data listed above.

The basic question that Life Tables ask is: given a set of observed age-specific mortality rates, what is the probability of dying by a given age x for someone currently aged less than x . Here, we substitute conversion for death. In demographic language, they are both one-time “decrements.”

The methodology is straightforward. We first estimate a set of age- and sex-specific conversion rates (equivalent to the M_x column in a Life Table) based on the 2022 data. Each of these rates is the number of women or men of a given age (x) who converted in 2022 divided by the number of women or men of the same age in 2022 in the population of potential converts, that is, those at risk of conversion. We define that population as Israel’s Other population.

We convert those rates into probabilities of conversion (q_x in a Life Table) and then apply them to a stationary population. That is, we start with a radix population of 100,000 people at age zero (the l_x column in a Life Table) and multiply it by the probability of converting between age 0 and 1. The population of potential converts at exact age 1 is then equivalent to the original 100,000 minus the number of converts at age 0 and 1 (the latter is equivalent to the d_x column in a Life Table). We multiply this by the conversion probability between age 1 and 2 to calculate the number of potential converts remaining at age 2. We replicate this series of calculations at each age up to the highest age of conversion.

The key advantage of this method is that it allows us to calculate the probability of conversion *at any age and by any age*, given current age-specific conversion rates and all conversions at younger ages. It is important to take the latter into account since, in the absence of migration, they reduce the potential number of converts in the same birth cohort in later periods. These probabilities are

estimated directly from the lx column (the column enumerating the number of remaining potential converts at every age).⁹

The probability of conversion

Selected probabilities of conversion in these Life Tables are presented in Table 2. The first two data columns contain the probabilities of conversion for girls and boys born in Israel or arriving shortly after birth who are classified as members of the Other population. The second set of columns contains the probabilities for girls and boys arriving in Israel at exact age 10, and the third for those arriving at exact age 18. In each of these cases, the numbers in the table refer to the probability of conversion by the age listed in the left-hand column.

Table 2. Probability of conversion by a given age for those arriving in Israel at ages 0, 10, and 18, by sex

Conversion by age	Born in Israel or arrives age 0		Arrives in Israel age 10		Arrives in Israel age 18	
	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male
5	0.076	0.064				
15	0.131	0.124	0.031	0.033		
25	0.375	0.219	0.302	0.137	0.266	0.092
35	0.459	0.270	0.396	0.194	0.365	0.151
45	0.493	0.296	0.434	0.223	0.405	0.182
55	0.509	0.312	0.453	0.240	0.424	0.200
65	0.523	0.327	0.468	0.257	0.440	0.218
75	0.533	0.348	0.479	0.280	0.452	0.242

Note: Life Table estimates based on 2022 data.

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: Life Table analysis of combined Population and Immigration Authority and CBS data

⁹ This method also has disadvantages. Notably, it applies the same probability to a person of a given age who has resided in Israel for 20 years as to a person of the same age who moved to Israel the previous year, where the latter's effective probability of conversion is zero, due to the time factors explained in footnote 7. That being said, any empirical effect of this problem should be quite marginal.

Overall, the probabilities in Table 2 point to high lifetime probabilities of conversion, especially for girls who are born in Israel or arrive in Israel at a young age. Specifically, assuming that age-specific conversion rates remain constant at their 2022 levels, a girl born in Israel (or who arrives shortly after birth) would have a 7.6% chance of undergoing conversion by age 5, and a 13.1% chance of undergoing conversion by age 15. As implied by the age pattern of conversion in Figure 1, her probability of conversion would then increase dramatically in her late teens and 20s. The same girl would have a 37.5% chance of converting by age 25, a 45.9% chance by age 35, and a 49.3% chance by age 45. The age-specific probabilities of conversion over the remaining decades of her life are very low, so the cumulative probability captured by the Life Table would then climb very slowly.

A girl who arrives in Israel at age 10 and is classified as belonging to the Other population obviously misses out on the probability of conversion at ages 0-9. However, her overall probabilities of converting by age 35 would remain relatively high because of the high age-specific rates beginning in the late teens. She would still have a roughly 40% chance of having converted by age 35. The equivalent probability for a woman who arrives in Israel at age 18 (and is classified as belonging to the Other population) would be 36.5%.

Applying these Life Table estimates of conversion to the current population of Other women gives us a very different picture of the magnitude of conversion than the one that we infer from Table 1. Specifically, according to the CBS, there were 121,494 Other women in Israel aged 0-39 in mid-2022. The CBS conversion data document 1,776 conversions by women in this age group in 2022. The Life Table allows us to calculate the share of women aged 0-39 in 2022 that will convert by the age of 40, assuming that current age-specific conversion rates remain constant. Of the 121,494 women, 30,878 women — roughly 25% of that total — will have converted by age 40, with roughly two thirds of these completing it by the age of 25.

For men, the cumulative probability of conversion is lower at every age, with the difference becoming particularly notable after people's teens. This is consistent with the female:male ratio of conversion by age shown in Figure 2. It also leads to a substantially lower cumulative number of conversions. Of the 127,008 men aged 0-39 in 2022, current age-specific conversion rates imply that 16,160 (12.7% of the total) will have converted by age 40, just over half of the female number in the same age group.

Table 3 presents an equivalent set of probabilities of conversion for women and men arriving in Israel at ages 30, 40, and 50. The probabilities over time are much lower than the estimates shown in Table 2, even when we compare the people over the same number of years. These differences are especially marked for women. For example, a woman arriving in Israel at age 40 would have a 10.4% probability of converting over the next 35 years (i.e., by age 75), less than a quarter of the probability (43.4%) of a girl arriving at age 10 converting over the same period (i.e., by age 45). For men, the comparable probabilities are 9.2% and 22.3% , respectively.

Table 3. Probability of conversion by a given age for those arriving in Israel at ages 30, 40, and 50, by sex

Conversion by age	Arrives in Israel age 30		Arrives in Israel age 40		Arrives in Israel age 50	
	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male
35	0.056	0.028				
45	0.116	0.063	0.028	0.020		
55	0.145	0.084	0.060	0.042	0.014	0.010
65	0.168	0.104	0.086	0.063	0.041	0.031
75	0.185	0.133	0.104	0.092	0.052	0.062

Note: Life Table estimates based on 2022 data.

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: Life Table analysis of combined Population and Immigration Authority and CBS data

The differences in probability of conversion between Tables 2 and 3, which respectively signal the lifetime conversion paths of younger and older members of the Other population, highlight the main reason that conversion is considered to be demographically insignificant. Relative to all other subpopulations in Israel, a larger share of Others are in their 40s–60s. At these ages, *conversion rates are less than one twentieth of their levels in people’s early 20s*. Failing to account for this difference in age structure yields a false conclusion.

Converts' fertility

The final demographic contribution of conversion comes from the additive effect of fertility in the second generation and, arguably, in every subsequent generation.

No publicly available data allow us to estimate converts' fertility in Israel — standard sources of data like the Israel Social Survey and Labor Force Survey do not identify people who have converted. We therefore estimate the demographic contribution of conversion through fertility with a simple simulation. Again, we focus on the 2022 data.

The lifetime number of births to converts is a product of two factors: the number of female converts (the number at risk of conversion multiplied by the conversion rate); and their post-conversion fertility.

The LT provides the first of these. We limit calculations to the 30,878 Other women in the 2022 data who will have converted by age 40. The number converting by age 27, and the additional numbers converting by 33, 37, and 40, are given in second column of Table 4. The assumed percentage of these women's children who are born Jewish is in the third column. We assume that 100% of children born to women who complete their conversion by exact age 27 are born Jewish, that this share drops to 75% for women who complete their conversion by age 33, and 50% and 25% for women who complete their conversion by ages 37 and 40, respectively.¹⁰

Table 4. Assumed number of Jewish births to the 30,878 women converts (by age 40) in Israel's 2022 Other population

Age x	Converted by age x	Percent of children born Jewish	Lifetime number of Jewish births given assumed completed fertility		
			2.0	2.5	3.0
27	21,429	100	54,011	67,514	81,017
33	5,167	75			
37	2,523	50			
40	1,759	25			

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: Life Table analysis of Population and Immigration Authority and CBS data

10 Shifting these percentages in a reasonable way does not change the substantive conclusions of this exercise.

The final columns of Table 4 contain the product of these estimations, each based on an assumed level of fertility, with these ranging from a low of 2.0 to a high of 3.0. Broadly, the lower number covers the average total fertility rates of Israel's combined secular and traditional nonreligious Jewish population, and the higher number the average of Israel's Jewish population in general (CBS, 2026). Given the convergence of immigrants' fertility to higher Israeli norms over time (Nahmias, 2004; Shifris & Okun, 2024), despite historically low levels of fertility within Israel's Other population, we think it more likely that the number of births will be toward the lower end of this spectrum, especially given the overall decline in fertility in Israel in the 2017–2023 period (Weinreb, 2023). However, some selection into a higher-fertility group could also be at work if, for example, one of the motives for conversion is associated with higher-fertility desires.

In either case, the estimates point to a substantial demographic impact of conversion. Over and above the conversion of the roughly 31,000 women themselves, conversion facilitates the addition of between 54,000 and 81,000 births to Israel's Jewish population across the lifetime of those women.

Robustness check

To check whether the 2022 conversion data used thus far are not outliers, we replicate these Life Table calculations on data from 2020 and 2021 (we do not replicate them for 2023 since the war in the final quartile of the year reduced the pace of conversion). Figure 3 graphs the probability of conversion by a given age for those arriving in Israel at age 0. In other words, these are the data in the first two columns of Table 2, but with discrete curves for each year.

Figure 3. Lifetime probability of conversion to Judaism by age for a cohort of Other females and males born in Israel or arriving in Israel prior to first birthday, given age-specific conversion rates in 2020, 2021, and 2022

Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: Life Table analysis of combined Population and Immigration Authority and CBS data

The figure confirms that estimates for women in 2022 are almost identical to those in 2021 and estimates for men are very similar: if anything, lifetime conversion rates for males based on 2021 data were marginally higher, with the difference emerging in late teens and early 20s. Conversion rates in 2022, therefore, were not outliers. If anything, that title belongs to 2020, when conversion rates were much lower. That is not surprising given the COVID-related closures that affected all Israeli institutions during that year. In fact, the higher rates in 2021 may in part reflect a compensating effect for lower rates in 2020.

We also replicate the calculations used to produce the fertility estimates in Table 4. Shown in Table 5, these point to somewhat larger differences between the years. The difference between 2022 and 2021 reflects the smaller absolute number of potential converts in 2021, despite an almost identical age-specific conversion rate. The larger difference between 2022 and 2020 reflects a combination of lower conversion rate and smaller pool of potential converts. In either case, even at the lower end of these estimates, conversion adds more than 40,000 children to the Jewish population.

Table 5. Estimated number of Jewish births to the women who convert in Israel by age 40, given rates of conversion in 2020, 2021, and 2022, and completed fertility of 2.0–3.0 children

	Number of converts to age 40	Lifetime number of Jewish births given assumed completed fertility		
		2.0	2.5	3.0
2020	24,010	41,717	52,146	62,575
2021	28,749	50,704	63,381	76,057
2022	30,878	54,011	67,514	81,017

Notes: Assumes the same percent of children born Jewish by age of mother as used in Table 4.
 Source: Alex Weinreb, Taub Center | Data: Life Table analysis of combined Population and Immigration Authority and CBS data

Summary and conclusions

The goal of this paper has been to evaluate the magnitude of conversion to Judaism in Israel and its effect on Israel's demography. The latter occur directly and through secondary effects arising from women converts' fertility. Based on age-specific conversion rates observed in the 2020–2022 period, roughly 40% of women and 25% of men who arrive in Israel as children and are classified as belonging to the Other population, convert to Judaism by age 30. Based on the 2021 and 2022 data, this amounts to around 35,000 people. This approximates the target set by Fisher (2015, p. 103) when he writes: "the conversion target should stabilize at around 40,000 people, with an emphasis on young people (up to age 30)." In addition, a large majority of these are women, and their children will be identified as Jewish.

Most reasonable observers would consider this magnitude of conversion to be socially and demographically significant, and to clearly signal the widespread assimilation into, and adoption of, Israeli identity in its dual national and religious domains. Some may see these patterns as a sign that the rebirth of a national Jewish home has revived long dormant patterns of conversion, including patterns that are reminiscent of ancient precedent. In the ancient world, Cohen (1983, p. 32) asserts, Judaism was unusual not only in allowing conversion — there was no equivalent in polytheistic religions of the time — but

also in incorporating a national aspect: "Philo and Josephus explicitly describe conversion to Judaism as the acquisition of a new citizenship (*politeia*)."

Many demographers will also see two additional truisms at work in these estimates. First, it is a reminder that meaningful demographic processes often play out slowly and over a long period. In this case, even if the total number of converts in Israel in any given year is relatively small, the cumulative effect across a lifecourse is demographically significant, at least for younger cohorts. Second, analysts need the right tools to be able to see these phenomena with any clarity. In this case, as I have shown, looking at a simple cross-sectional data table misleads more than it informs. It presents a picture of failure when, in fact, there has been considerable success.

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